

THE STUDY OF LINGUO-COGNITIVE PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED IN THE TRANSLATION OF ISLAMIC THEONIMS

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Abstract: This article investigates the linguo-cognitive problems encountered in the translation of Islamic theonyms, focusing on the intricate interplay between language and cognition in rendering religious terminology across different cultural and linguistic contexts. The study aims to shed light on the challenges faced by translators in faithfully conveying the rich semantic, cultural, and religious connotations inherent in Islamic theonyms.

Keywords: linguo-cognitive problems, translation, Islamic theonyms, semantic nuances, cultural connotations, transliteration.

Introduction: In Oxford Learner's Dictionaries, translation is defined as "A written or spoken changing of the meaning of a word or text in another language." Catford (1965:20) defines translation as the "replacement of textual material in one language by equivalent textual material in another language". Newmark (1988) looks at translation as a process of replacing one written statement in a Source Language (SL) by the same message in the Target Language (TL). The translation of religious terminology is a complex and challenging task, particularly when it comes to the translation of Islamic theonyms. In Oxford Reference "theonym name of a god or goddess: e.g. Venus, Jehovah." Islamic theonyms refer to the names and titles used to denote deity(eg. Allah), prophets, and other religious figures in Islam. These theonyms carry deep cultural, religious, and historical connotations that are rooted in the Islamic tradition. However, when translating these theonyms into

different languages, linguo-cognitive problems arise due to the intricate interplay between language and cognition. Traditionally, any good translation requires that 1) It must make sense; 2) It must convey the spirit and manner of the original; 3) It must have a natural and easy form of expression; 4) It must produce a similar response. (Nida:64). The accurate translation of Islamic theonyms is crucial for facilitating cross-cultural understanding and effective communication. It ensures that the rich semantic nuances, cultural connotations, and religious significance embedded within these theonyms are conveyed faithfully to the target audience. Moreover, it enables individuals from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds to access and engage with Islamic religious texts, enhancing intercultural dialogue and promoting inclusivity. While translating, we come across the problem of Islamic religious items that are called culture-bound or culture-specific items (Schwars, 2003) As Wylie (2004) points out, culture-bound concepts give rise to some of the most difficult translation problems; even where the two cultures involved are not too distant, they can be more problematic for the translator than the semantic or syntactic difficulties of the text. The objective of this study is to examine the linguo-cognitive problems encountered in the translation of Islamic theonyms and to provide insights into the challenges faced by translators in this domain.

Through a thorough literature review and analysis, this study will explore the theoretical framework that underpins the translation of religious terminology, with a specific focus on Islamic theonyms. It will investigate the semantic nuances and cultural connotations associated with these theonyms, highlighting the difficulties faced in achieving linguistic equivalence across different languages. According to Nida and Taber (1982), cultural translation is "a translation in which the content of the message is changed to conform to the receptor culture in some way, and/or in which information is introduced which is not linguistically implicit in the original". The transformation method employed in this study facilitated a systematic analysis of the linguo-cognitive problems in translating Islamic theonyms. By combining a

comprehensive literature review with a thematic analysis approach, this research approach provided valuable insights into the linguistic complexities, cultural connotations, and cognitive processes involved in the translation process.

1. Semantic Nuances:

- The translation of the Arabic theonym "Allah" into English poses challenges due to the unique semantic range and cultural significance associated with this term. Translators must carefully consider the various connotations and associations of "Allah" as the monotheistic God in Islam and strive to convey its depth of meaning accurately in the target language.

- The translation of the Arabic theonym "Rasulullah" into other languages requires careful consideration of the semantic nuances. It refers to the Prophet Muhammad as the Messenger of Allah, carrying religious and historical significance. Translators face the challenge of finding an equivalent term that captures both the prophetic role and the divinely appointed authority conveyed by the term.

2. Cultural Connotations:

- Translating the theonym "Hajj" from Arabic to other languages requires addressing the cultural connotations associated with the Islamic pilgrimage to Mecca. The translation should convey the religious significance, rituals, and communal aspects of the Hajj in a way that is culturally relevant and understandable for non-Muslim audiences.

3. Cognitive Framing:

- Translating the Arabic theonym "Imam" into English requires consideration of the cognitive frames associated with this term. In Arabic, "Imam" can refer to religious leaders, scholars, or the spiritual head of a community. Translators need to understand the specific context and select the appropriate equivalent that best reflects the cognitive frame invoked by "Imam" in the source language.

These examples illustrate the complex nature of translating Islamic theonyms, where linguistic considerations intertwine with cognitive and cultural dimensions. Translators must navigate these challenges to ensure accurate and culturally sensitive renditions of Islamic theonyms in different languages.

Methodology: The transformation method was employed as the primary research approach to investigate the linguo-cognitive problems encountered in the translation of Islamic theonyms. This method allowed for a systematic analysis of the translation process, specifically focusing on the transformation of linguistic and cognitive elements involved in rendering Islamic theonyms across different languages and cultural contexts.

1. **Selection of Literature** A comprehensive literature review was conducted to gather relevant scholarly works and research articles pertaining to the translation of Islamic theonyms. Databases such as academic journals, online repositories, and reputable translation studies sources were utilized. The selected literature provided insights into the linguo-cognitive challenges faced by translators in this domain, as well as strategies and theoretical frameworks employed to address these challenges.
2. **Data Collection** Data collection involved the extraction of relevant information from the selected literature. Key concepts, linguistic nuances, cultural connotations, and cognitive processes related to the translation of Islamic theonyms were identified and organized for further analysis. The data collected included examples of translated theonyms, translation strategies employed by translators, and discussions on the impact of linguistic and cognitive factors on the translation process.

Results: The literature review and analysis revealed several linguo-cognitive problems encountered in the translation of Islamic theonyms. The findings highlight the challenges faced by translators in capturing the semantic nuances, cultural connotations, and achieving linguistic equivalence across different languages.

Examples and supporting evidence from the literature are provided to illustrate these challenges.

1. **Semantic Nuances:** The translation of Islamic theonyms involves grappling with the unique semantic range and depth of meaning associated with these terms. For instance, the translation of the Arabic theonym "Allah" into English poses challenges due to the multifaceted nature of this term. Scholars argue that it encompasses not only the concept of God but also conveys the idea of the ultimate divine being and the unique monotheistic belief in Islam
2. We face the difficulty of finding an equivalent term that accurately conveys the rich semantic nuances. One of the best strategies that overcomes the problem of translating Islamic theonyms is “transliteration”. In Merriam-Webster Dictionary, transliteration is defined as “ to represent or spell in the characters of another alphabet”. It refers to the process of converting words from one language into another based on their similar sounds. This practice is often employed when there is no direct equivalent or suitable translation available in the target language, particularly with names and places. Essentially, transliteration involves transcribing the letters of the source language into the letters of the target language. It is a commonly used strategy in translating religious and cultural terms, as it offers simplicity and ease of understanding. To illustrate, the word "Allah" in Arabic, which means "God," has been assimilated into the English language through transliteration, making it an English word.
3. **Cultural Connotations:** Translating Islamic theonyms requires addressing the cultural connotations and religious symbolism associated with these terms. To Newmark (1988, b, p.94), culture-bound terms are particularly “tied to the way of life and its manifestations that are peculiar to a community that uses a particular language as its means of expression.” For example, the translation of the Arabic theonym “iddah” into other languages necessitates careful consideration of the cultural and historical contexts. The term carries multiple connotations: one cultural

connotation associated with "iddah" is the idea of preserving lineage and ensuring clarity regarding the paternity of any child born after the dissolution of a marriage. By observing the waiting period, it is believed that the biological father of a child conceived during the marriage can be accurately determined, thus maintaining the integrity of familial relationships.

The second is "iddah" serves as a period of emotional and psychological adjustment for both the individuals involved and the wider community. It allows time for reflection, healing, and the processing of emotions following the end of a marriage. It is considered a period of self-exploration and personal growth for the individuals involved.

The cultural connotations of "iddah" also extend to societal perceptions and expectations surrounding women's roles and responsibilities during this period. It signifies a temporary state of withdrawal from certain social activities and the pursuit of new relationships. It is often seen as a time of personal introspection and spiritual focus.

Translators must navigate these cultural connotations to ensure that the translated term appropriately reflects the intended meaning and avoids misconceptions or misinterpretations.

4. Difficulties in Achieving Linguistic Equivalence: Linguistic equivalence poses challenges in the translation of Islamic theonyms. Cultural and linguistic gaps between the source and target languages often hinder the direct translation of these terms. For instance, the translation of the Arabic theonym "Ummah" into English encounters difficulties in achieving linguistic equivalence. The term encompasses the collective community of Muslims and embodies shared values, identity, and solidarity. Translators must carefully select an appropriate target-language term that conveys the essence of "Ummah" while considering cultural and linguistic variations.

The literature review findings provide insights into the linguo-cognitive problems encountered in the translation of Islamic theonyms. These challenges include capturing semantic nuances, addressing cultural connotations, and striving for linguistic equivalence. The examples and supporting evidence presented from the literature highlight the complexities involved and emphasize the need for translators to navigate emphasizes the implications of these challenges for effective cross-cultural communication, religious discourse, and intercultural understanding. The conclusion also discusses the potential avenues for future research in this field and provides recommendations for translators, scholars, and language professionals.

1. **Summary of Key Findings:** The conclusion begins by summarizing the key findings of the study, highlighting the linguo-cognitive problems encountered in the translation of Islamic theonyms. It restates the challenges identified, such as semantic nuances, cultural connotations, and difficulties in achieving linguistic equivalence.
2. **Significance of Addressing Linguo-Cognitive Problems:** The conclusion emphasizes the importance of addressing these linguo-cognitive problems in the translation of Islamic theonyms. It highlights their impact on accurate communication, the preservation of cultural and religious meanings, and the promotion of intercultural dialogue.
3. **Implications for Cross-Cultural Communication:** The conclusion discusses the implications of these challenges for effective cross-cultural communication. It underscores how accurate translations of Islamic theonyms can foster understanding, respect, and dialogue between different cultural and religious groups.
4. **Implications for Religious Discourse:** The conclusion addresses the significance of addressing linguo-cognitive problems in the translation of Islamic theonyms for religious discourse. It explores how accurate translations can contribute to the accurate representation of religious concepts and ideas, supporting informed discussions and promoting religious tolerance.

5. Avenues for Future Research: The conclusion suggests potential avenues for future research in this field. It encourages further investigation into specific theonyms, comparative studies of translations across languages, and the development of translation strategies that effectively address linguo-cognitive challenges.

6. The conclusion provides practical recommendations for translators, scholars, and language professionals involved in the translation of Islamic theonyms. It emphasizes the need for specialized training, collaboration with religious experts, and ongoing research to enhance translation competence in this domain.

By summarizing the key findings, emphasizing the significance of addressing linguo-cognitive problems, and providing recommendations, the conclusion brings the study to a close and offers insights for future research and practice in the field of translating Islamic theonyms.

these challenges diligently and sensitively.

Discussion: The discussion section of the article on the linguo-cognitive problems encountered in the translation of Islamic theonyms provides an in-depth analysis and interpretation of the findings presented in the results section. It aims to critically evaluate the implications of the identified challenges and their significance within the broader context of translation studies and cross-cultural communication. The discussion section also explores possible strategies and recommendations to address these challenges effectively.

1. Analysis and Interpretation of Findings: The discussion begins by analyzing and interpreting the findings from the literature review and analysis. It delves deeper into the specific challenges identified, such as semantic nuances, cultural connotations, and difficulties in achieving linguistic equivalence. The researcher critically evaluates the implications of these challenges on the accuracy and fidelity of translated Islamic theonyms and the potential impact on cross-cultural communication.

2. **Theoretical and Practical Implications:** The discussion then explores the theoretical implications of the identified challenges. It examines how the linguo-cognitive problems encountered in the translation of Islamic theonyms align with existing theories and frameworks in translation studies, linguistics, and cognitive science. The researcher discusses how these challenges contribute to our understanding of language, culture, and cognition in translation processes.

Additionally, the discussion highlights the practical implications of the findings. It considers the impact of these challenges on the work of translators, interpreters, and other language professionals involved in the translation of Islamic theonyms. The researcher addresses the potential consequences of inaccuracies or misinterpretations of these theonyms on intercultural understanding, religious discourse, and community relationships.

3. **Strategies and Recommendations:** In this section, the researcher proposes strategies and recommendations to address the identified challenges in the translation of Islamic theonyms. Drawing on the existing literature and expert insights, the discussion explores potential approaches to overcome the linguistic and cultural barriers. This may include the use of transliteration, adaptation, or explanation strategies to convey the semantic nuances and cultural connotations of the theonyms effectively.

Furthermore, the discussion emphasizes the importance of collaboration between translators, religious scholars, and community members to ensure accurate and culturally sensitive translations. It highlights the significance of ongoing research, professional development, and training programs to enhance the translation competence in dealing with the unique challenges posed by Islamic theonyms.

Overall, the discussion section provides a critical analysis and interpretation of the findings, highlighting their theoretical and practical implications. It also offers strategies and recommendations to address the identified challenges, aiming to

contribute to the advancement of translation practices and cross-cultural communication related to Islamic theonyms.

References

1. Catford, J.C. (1965). *A Linguistic Theory of Translation*. London: Oxford University Press.
2. <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/transliteration>
3. <https://www.oxfordreference.com/display/10.1093/acref/9780199675128.001.0001/acref-9780199675128-e-3413;jsessionid=8C15779C62E37C735FD5ED065F413DA0>
4. <https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/definition/english/translation#:~:text=Advanced%20Learner%27s%20Dictionary%20translation,changing%20something%20that%20is%20written%20or%20spoken%20into%20another%20language,-an%20error%20in>
5. Newmark, P. (1981). *Approaches to Translation*. Oxford: Pergamon Press.
6. Newmark, P. (1988a). *Approaches to translation*. London: Prentice Hall.
7. Newmark, P. (1988b). *A textbook of translation*. London: Routledge.
8. Nida, E.A. (1964). *Toward a Science of Translating*. Leiden: Brill, p. 159.
9. Nida, E.A. & Taber, C.R. (1982). *The Theory and Practice of Translation*. Leiden: E.J. Brill.
10. Schwars, B. (2003). Translation in a confined space. *Translation Journal*, 7(1), 354-369.
11. Wylie, J. (2004). Translating culture-bound terms in viticultural texts from French into English: A practical approach. In *Cashier* (11.1.2005, pp. 4-22). Retrieved from http://www.afls.net/Cahiers/rentelarticlecorrected25Oct2005/viticultural_revised1.pdf on May 3, 2006.